

A Study of Impact on Digitalization on “Online Consumer Behavior” Concerning Adidas- India

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: November

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Ashwini, K., et al.
“A Study of Impact on Digitalization on ‘Online Consumer Behavior’ Concerning Adidas- India.” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science & Humanities*, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 191–99.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3575333>

Dr. K. Ashwini

*Associate Professor & Co-ordinator, Department of Post Graduate Studies
Jain College, Bangalore*

Suhas Guptha & Wahid Baig

Student- Jain College, Vasavi Temple Road, V.V Puram, Bengaluru

Abstract

In the era of digitalization in Online marketing where the marketing concept is consumer-oriented, and the emphasis is more on the consumer rather than on the product. The essence of modern marketing lies with the customers, whose needs and desires have to be coordinated with the set of products and production programs. Therefore a study is undertaken to marketing success an enterprise depends as its ability to create a community of satisfied consumers. All the business activities should be carried out in ways that are directed towards the customer satisfaction of the needs.

Keywords: Consumer-oriented, Consumer Satisfaction, Production Programs.

Introduction

It is a globally accepted fact that in recent times, marketers have become dynamic, and the consumer has control over the strategic decisions made by the insurance companies. Companies are put to challenge to understand the pulses of digital age policy holders and their buying patterns. India, in this scenario, is no exception. It is being a nation of diverse cultures and a tradition; understanding the consumer buying patterns becomes a hard task. Therefore there are several marketing competitors such as NIKE, PUMA, etc.

History

The history of consumer behavior seems to be highly intertwined with the history of marketing thought. The purpose of this paper is to trace the historical dependence and allegiance of consumer behavior on the discipline and practice of marketing. It then attempts to – forecast emerging trends in consumer behavior research and theory as a consequence a new and emerging schools of marketing thought.

Over the years, marketing has shifted its reliance on other disciplines as well as its focus on understanding. Consumer behavior emerged the 1940s and 1950s as a distinct sub- discipline in the marketing area.

Consumer behavior is an inter social science that blends elements from psychology, sociology, social anthropology, anthropology, ethnography, marketing, and economics, especially behavioral economics.

Marketing kept its focus on individual customers but began to borrow more and more from the behavioral science. This resulted in what we call as the behavioral school of marketing thoughts. Marketing has begun to shift its attention away from the individual customers and concentrate on the markets. In this process, it is also relying less on the behavioral sciences and more on the traditional social sciences. We shall call this emerging trend an adaptive school of marketing thought.

Digitalization

Digitalization is the integration of digital technologies into everyday life by the digitization of everything that can be digitized. The literal meaning of digitalization gives an apparent idea of development and technology dependent- world.

ADIDAS

It refers to the line of casual clothes and new campaign launch by ADIDAS around the beginning of 2008. “ADIDAS ORIGINALS” was known as “ADIDAS HERITAGE”. The name was changed to ORIGINALS in the year 1980.

ADIDAS originals invite today’s lifestyle consumers to celebrate originality through an exceptional brand campaign and a variety of product themes inspired by the rich sporting heritage of ADIDAS and the global reach of the Trefoil.

Adidas Marketing Strategy

ADIDAS has a clear mission-“to be the leading sports brand in the world.” To accomplish this mission, the brand comprises two divisions that reflect two distinct market segments: sports performance and sports style. ADIDAS becomes something that makes you better. Not just as an athlete, but as a sports man and a better human being. ADIDAS is a very popular brand and has a large market share. ADIDAS is like Nike, very active in securing sponsorships advertising deals with celebrities.

Adidas Slogan

“IMPOSSIBLE IS NOTHING” is the current main stream marketing slogan for ADIDAS. This campaign was developed by TBWA based in Amsterdam but also with significant work being done by TBWA\Chiat\Day in San Francisco – particularly for its basketball campaign “Believe in Five.”

ADIDAS, the first sportswear brand in INDIA to cross the 1000 Crore revenue mark. ADIDAS has managed to grow the net profit of its India’s business by 53% in 2017-18. By taking its margin beyond the 10% mark, which no multinational in this space could cross across the years. Its net profit stood at RS 1.74 billion compared to RS 1.13 billion years ago. NIKE also failed to turn the profitability between 2014-15 to 2017-18. In 2017-18 ADIDAS, India’s operating revenue clinched at RS 10.79 billion. It had become a multinational sportswear brand. Many of the consumers would prefer this brand due to the quality and durability ADIDAS has set up a trademark in the consumer’s mind, and it satisfies all their needs and wants. The advertisement was given by the ADIDAS with celebrities also inspires and attracts the people to buy it.

How much is the Company Investing in Digitalization?

ADIDAS approaches the whole notion of digitalization. It had said that e-commerce would be worth of 2million\$ under the previous plan, but when it came back to the market it would double to 4million\$ by 2020. It has started hiring hundreds of engineers and software engineers to help out.

\$211 million was invested by the ADIDAS group in 2017 in research and development. By 57% ADIDAS Group increases its e-commerce sales. ADIDAS is turning out to be a much more software company than it used to be.

A digital push in production something called as Speed Factory

Products can be produced in a factory that is fully automated and requires very few people. Launched the first one in ANSBACH and have just opened its second one in ATLANTA. The robots can knit the shoes and attach the outsole and also prints the brand logo on the product. Robots can pass the products from one machine to another machine, basically without involving a human labor. Packing can also be done although transportation has to be done by people.

Material innovations can be done by various combination of engineers, product designers, etc.. ADIDAS group works about more than 2-3 years to bring up new technologies in terms of the products. It also has a high degree of Independence Company, which can bring up a few more ideas to develop or design new products.

Why is ADIDAS Famous?

1. ADIDAS is the only logo with a function. Just the three stripes
2. It has the most and the best classics in the archive
3. ADIDAS wrote Hip-Hop history with Beastie Boys.
4. ADIDAS has to boost up sales with cushioning innovation.

Why the Study?

ADIDAS has provided more effective designs and good quality products to the customers, but still, this facility is not affected by most of the customers. The main problem associated with ADIDAS company is there are many competitors (NIKE, PUMA) in the market. Therefore, this study has been done to undertaken to know the pros and cons of ADIDAS products in the minds of the consumer.

Objectives of the Study

1. To identify the perception of the consumers.
2. To identify various factors affecting purchases.
3. To study consumer buying behavior.
4. To understand the distribution network.

Limitations of the Study

1. When the buyers are busy, we cannot get accurate data from them.
2. According to the time limit of our project, we could cover only a few areas.
3. During the survey, some respondents did not give an answer in a proper manner.

Research and Methodology

Sampling method: Convenience method

Sample size: 50

Data: Primary data

Sampling technique: questionnaire

Data Analysis and Interpretation

We have surveyed about 50 consumers about ADIDAS products, who were students, teachers, and other professionals. The research studied the various types of ADIDAS products in which most of them have preferred shoes (55.6%). Many of them described the product as average and great. Quality is the main determinant in the ADIDAS products. As the advertisements are attractive many would like to purchase ADIDAS products.

Table 1 Gender of respondents
Table showing the age of respondents

Respondents	Percentage
Male	28.3%
Female	71.7%
Total	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 1 Gender of Respondents
Chart showing age of Respondents

Source: Primary Data

Discussion

It can be seen that out of 100%. Female respondents were 71.7% ,and males were 28.3%. We can analyze that female respondents are more than male respondents as females are interested in buying ADIDAS products than males.

Table 2 Occupation of Respondents
Table showing the occupation of Respondents.

Respondents	Percentage
Teachers	4.27
Student	80.9%
Businessman	2.03
Others	12.8%
Total	100%

Source: primary data

Chart 2 Occupation of Respondents
Chart showing the Occupation of Respondents.

Source: Primary Data

Discussion

It can be seen that, out of 100%, of the respondents, students use (80.9%), teachers use (4.27%), businessman use (2.03%), others use (12.8%), respectively. As 80% of the respondents are youths, they are more interested in buying ADIDAS products than other professional people. As youths are more interested in buying ADIDAS products because of their quality, brand, and also for product designs. The other 20% professional people are showing less interest in ADIDAS products.

Table 3: Respondents using the type of ADIDAS Products
Table showing people using ADIDAS products

Respondents	Percentage
Shoes	55.3%
Outfits	25.5%
Bags	23.4%
Sports Equipment	8.5%
Total	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 3: Respondents using the type of, ADIDAS Products
Chart showing People using ADIDAS Products

Source: Primary Data

Discussion

From the above table ,we can say that the consumer prefers ADIDAS shoes more (55.3%), outfits come the second with (25.5%), bags are used around (23.4%) and sports equipment are the least amongst all (8.5%). The majority of the people opt for ADIDAS shoes because of brand names and various designs. They have a variety of choices. Outfits, bags ,and sports equipment are purchased less compared to others.

Table 4. Respondents showing Navigation of Products
Table showing Navigation of Product by Consumers

Respondents	Percentage
1 Star	4.3%
2 Star	6.4%
3 Star	42.6%
4 Star	36.2%
5 Star	10.6%
Total	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 4: Respondents showing Navigation of Products
Chart showing Navigation of Product by Consumers

Source: Primary Data

Discussion

From the above chart we can say that, (4.3%) have rated 1 star, (6.4%) have rated 2 stars, and (42.6%), (36.2%), and (10.6%) have rated 3 stars, 4 stars and 5 stars respectively. It can be further seen that most of them rate around 3 stars in case of navigating the product. ADIDAS should improve in this matter.

Table 5 Respondents’ Description of ADIDAS Products
Table showing Products description by Consumers

Respondents	Percentage
Terrible	2.1%
Average	44.7%
Life-Saving	25.5%
Great	29.8%
Total	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 5: Respondents Describing about ADIDAS Products
Chart showing Products Description by Consumers

Which of the following words would you like to describe our product?
 47 responses

Source: Primary Data

Discussion

From the above table we can interpret that out of 100% respondents maximum number of them describe average(44.7%), consumers who say it as life- saving are (25.5%), The above graph can be analyzed as consumers describes ADIDAS products as average is more than life- saving and great. Very few of them says it’s terrible also.

Table 6: Respondents Influenced by Particular ADIDAS Product
Table showing factors influencing ADIDAS Products

Respondents	Percentage
Quality	59.6%
Durability	34%
Price	17%
Variety	8.5%
Total	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 6: Respondents influenced by Particular ADIDAS Product
Chart Showing Factors Influencing ADIDAS Products

What factors influence you to go to a particular ADIDAS product?
 47 responses

Source: Primary Data

Discussion

From the above data we can interpret that (59.6%) of the consumers go by quality, (34%) of them are influenced by durability,(17%) influenced by price,(8.5%) go by variety. On the basis of the above graph, we can analyze that ADIDAS products are mostly influenced by the quality and

consumers say variety is less as compared with durability and price. ADIDAS products should include variety and new designs in the products.

Table 7 Respondents wearing ADIDAS shoes
Tables showing the consumers wearing ADIDAS shoes

Respondents	Percentage
Yes	78.3%
No	17.4%
May Be	4.3%
Total	100%

Source: Primary data

Chart 7 Respondents wearing ADIDAS shoes
Chart showing the Consumers Wearing ADIDAS shoes

Source: Primary Data

Discussion

It can be seen from the above data that consumers wearing ADIDAS shoes are (78.3%), not wearing (17.4%), may be or may not be (4.3%). We can further analyze that most of them would prefer wearing ADIDAS shoes. Some of them say may be we can conclude that in future they may buy or may not buy.

Findings

1. Majority of the ADIDAS products are purchased by the female (71.7%) rather than males (28.3%)
2. The majority of the customers for ADIDAS are students, which is 80.9%. This helps us to know which profession of people a major customer of ADIDAS
3. The majority of the customers precisely visit ADIDAS for shoes (55.3%), outfits (25.5%), bags (23.4%).
4. The majority of the customer navigate the product between 3 stars to 5 stars (30-50%).
5. The majority of the consumer’s opinion about ADIDAS products is average which is 44.7%.
6. The analysis reveals the majority of the consumers are influenced by the quality of the ADIDAS products which is 59.6%.
7. The majority of the people would like to wear ADIDAS shoe which is 78.3%.

Conclusion

ADIDAS is a very good brand. Since it is ranked 1st out of the other brands mentioned, it is understood that ADIDAS, is liked by the customers and hence it is more familiar and popular. The quality and services provided here in ADIDAS are satisfactory to the customers.

Since most of the customers fall under the age group which belongs to the student category and, more students are likely to buy ADIDAS products. Hence ADIDAS is student- friendly.

Hence we conclude that by saying, other than the price being expensive, all other attributes of ADIDAS are satisfied by the customers which influence them to go in for ADIDAS products.

Suggestions

1. After analyzing and interpreting the opinions given by the customers, comments that ADIDAS is an expensive product.
2. Price should be reduced than the actual price, in order to reach middle- class people, so that even they afford to buy ADIDAS products.
3. According to convenience sampling, the customers suggest that ADIDAS must come up with varieties of products with good models and designs.
4. ADIDAS should come up with more attractive advertisements to catch the eyes of the customers.

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